

**A PRELIMINARY PHONOLOGICAL SKETCH OF
VA, AN ANGKUIC LANGUAGE**

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1. Introduction

The Northern Va language belongs to the Angkuic subgroup of the Palaungic branch of Austroasiatic (Hsiu 2015), and is spoken in Mojiang County of south-central Yunnan Province, China. The language name Va comes from the the speakers' self-designated name (autonym), *vaʔ⁵¹*. Despite the speakers having the autonym *vaʔ⁵¹*, the Va language does not belong to the Waic subgroup. Va is also tonal unlike most Waic languages. Although this paper specifically describes Northern Va and not Southern Va, Northern Va will simply be referred to as *Va* in this paper. Unless noted otherwise, *Va* is used to Northern Va and not Southern Va specifically.

Speakers of Va are classified as ethnic Bulang by the Chinese government, and are also locally referred to by neighboring ethnic groups as the Bulang people (Hsiu 2015). According to my informant, there are about 600 Va households comprising approximately 2,000 individuals in Taihe Administrative Village 太和行政村 in Jingxing Township 景星乡, Mojiang County, Yunnan Province, China. The language is spoken vigorously by all age groups, including children. From my personal observations in the Va villages, on the EGIDS scale, Va would be considered to be at 6a (vigorous), but may be leaning towards 6b (threatened) due to widespread urban migration to Kunming city and Guangdong province.

The only previous documentation of Va is that of Simao (1990), an unpublished Chinese internal government manuscript¹. Although Simao (1990) and I both have Va lexical data from the same village of Wamo, Simao (1990) differs significantly from mine. I have not found Simao (1990) to be usable since it contains many transcription errors.

Since no comprehensive sociolinguistic surveys or intelligibility tests have yet been conducted, it cannot be said if Northern Va and Southern Va are indeed separate languages. For now, the name “Va” will be used. No ISO 639-3 code exists for Northern Va as of now.

The internal classification of Va within the Austroasiatic family is as follows (Hsiu 2015).

- Family: Austroasiatic
- Branch: Palaungic
- Subgroup: Angkuic
- Subdivision: Eastern

¹ I would like to thank Harald Hammerström of the Max Plank Institute in Nijmegen, Netherlands for bringing my attention to this resource.

The location of Mojiang County, Yunnan, where Va is spoken, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Location of Mojiang County within China. Va is spoken in Jingxing Township in west-central Mojiang County. Source: Wikimedia Commons <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Location_of_Mojiang_within_Yunnan_%28China%29.png>. Accessed 15 August 2015.

1.1 Data collection

The Northern Va data was collected on April 10, 2014, in the village of Wamo 挖墨 in Taihe Administrative Village 太和村, Jingxing Township 景星乡, Mojiang County 墨江县, Yunnan Province, China. Audio recordings were made using an Audio-Technica ATR2100-USB cardioid unidirectional microphone and Acer Aspire One 10.1-inch laptop. Audacity (version 2.1.0), an audio recording and editing software program, was used to record WAV files.² I elicited the data using Standard Mandarin Chinese (also called Putonghua), and the recordings then were glossed by myself in English.

² WAV audio recordings are available from the author upon request.

During April 10-11, 2014, I recorded about 270 lexical items from Northern Va and about 100 lexical items from Southern Va, with 246 lexical items from Northern Va presented for analysis in this paper. Both are spoken in several scattered villages in Jingxing Township 景星乡, Mojiang County, Yunnan, China. Southern Va is spoken only by middle-age and elderly people, but not by children. It is more conservative and retains many sequisyllabic prefixes, particularly /s-/, which are not retained in Northern Va. Northern Va, which is also vigorously spoken by children, may have about 2,000 speakers, and for Southern Va, perhaps just under 1,000. The Va of Mojiang County are geographically isolated from other Austroasiatic-speaking groups, as no other Austroasiatic languages are spoken within perhaps a 100-km radius.

My Northern Va informant, surnamed Li 李, is a 27-year-old male shopkeeper who is fluent in Putonghua (standard Mandarin), Southwestern Mandarin, and Va. He has worked in Kunming for a few years before. According to Li, the ancestors of the Va were also called “Mang 莽” in the past, and had migrated from the Dali area, which is located much further to the northwest. My Southern Va informant is 42-year-old Wang Lijuan 王丽娟. Data collection on Southern Va was performed under time constraints, since it was done during a bus break by the side of a road while I was on my way to the Mojiang county seat.

My Northern Va informant claimed that Southern Va is very difficult for him to understand, but my Southern Va informant reported that she understands Northern Va perfectly well.

Locals of Jingxing Township reported that Va is in contact with Southwestern Mandarin, Kaduo (*kha31 tu31*), and Tai Ya.

1.2 Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Dr. Paul Sidwell (Australian National University), Dr. Harald Hammarström (Max Planck Institute), Ajarn Phinnarat Akharawatthanakun (Payap University), and many other scholars and colleagues for the helpful assistance and discussion along the way. I am also deeply indebted to the Va people of Mojiang County, China for the generous time and assistance that they had provided me during my 2014 field trip. Without them, this paper would not have been possible.

2. Phone inventory

Va has a phone inventory of 29 consonants, 7 vowels, and 4 tones. Some notable features include 4 voiceless nasals ([m̥], [n̥], [ɲ̥], [ŋ̥]) and nasalized vowels, all of which are contrastive. The phone inventory presented here is also the phonemic inventory of Va, since no phones have been found to exist only as allophones in all environments.

2.1 Consonants

The 29 consonants in Va are as follows. All unaspirated voiceless stops are contrastive with aspirated voiceless stops, and all voiced nasals also contrastive with voiceless nasals.

Table 1: Consonant inventory

	<i>bilabial</i>	<i>labiodental</i>	<i>alveolar</i>	<i>retroflex</i>	<i>alveolar-palatal</i>	<i>palatal</i>	<i>velar</i>	<i>glottal</i>
<i>voiceless stop</i>	p		t				k	ʔ
<i>aspirated voiceless stop</i>	p ^h		t ^h				k ^h	
<i>voiceless nasal</i>	m̥		n̥			ɲ̥	ŋ̥	
<i>voiced nasal</i>	m		n			ɲ	ŋ	
<i>voiceless fricative</i>		f	s	ʂ	ç		x	h
<i>voiced fricative</i>		v			ʝ		ɣ	
<i>approximant</i>		w						
<i>voiceless affricate</i>					tç			
<i>voiced affricate</i>					dʝ			
<i>lateral</i>		l						
<i>lateral fricative</i>		ɬ						

Note that the the alveolo-palatal affricates [tʃ], [dʒ], [tʃ], and [dʒ] are somewhat more fronted than [tʃ], [dʒ], [tʃ], and [dʒ].

There is also only one example of [pʰ], *na⁵¹* ‘laugh, to’.

No voiced alveolar fricative [z] has been observed to contrast with the voiceless alveolar fricative [s] in Va, even though there are 3 voiced fricatives, [v], [z], and [ɣ] constrating with the voiceless fricatives [f], [ç], and [x].

2.1.1 Consonant clusters

There are 5 consonant clusters in Va, which are always in the initial position and take on the syllabic structure CC-.

Table 2: Consonant clusters

<i>Unaspirated</i>	<i>Aspirated</i>
pl-	p ^h l-
kl-	k ^h l-
	p ^h j-

The lateral clusters *p^(h)l-* and *k^(h)l-* are likely due to contact with neighboring Tai languages at a time before they lost their consonant clusters. Today, most modern-day Tai languages in the area have no consonant clusters. Note that there are no [tl]- or [t^hl]- clusters in Va.

There is also one consonant cluster that takes on a glide instead of a liquid, namely *p^hj-*. This is because this initial often occurs with diphthongs. Analyzing it as *p^hi-* would cause the nucleus to be analyzed as a triphthong (VVV) instead of a diphthong (VV), which would be more consistent with the other words that can only have monophthongs and diphthongs.

2.2 Vowels

There are 7 contrastive vowels in Va.

Table 3: Vowel inventory

	<i>front</i>	<i>central</i>	<i>back</i> <i>unrounded</i>	<i>back</i> <i>rounded</i>
<i>high</i>	i	ɨ	ɯ	u
<i>high-mid</i>	e		ɤ	o
<i>low</i>	a			

In Va, there apparently is free (rather than allophonic) variation between [a] and [ɑ], and [ɤ] and [ə]. [a] has been transcribed instead of [ɑ], since the low vowel tends to have more of a front quality more often than a back one. As for [ɤ], it has a front quality

2.2.1 Nasalized vowels

All vowels can also be nasalized, as shown in Table 3.

Table 4: Nasalized vowels

	<i>front</i>	<i>central</i>	<i>back</i> <i>unrounded</i>	<i>back</i> <i>rounded</i>
<i>high</i>	ĩ	ɨ̃	ũ	ũ
<i>high-mid</i>	ẽ		ɥ̃	õ
<i>low</i>	ã			

2.2.2 Diphthongs

There are 6 diphthongs in Va, as listed below.

- -ua
- -ui
- -ei
- -ɤi
- -ie
- -ou

All diphthongs can also be nasalized, as *-ũa*, *-ũi*, *-ẽi*, *-iẽ*, *-ĩi*, and *-õu*.

2.3 Tones

There are 4 tones in Va, 1 of which is level and 3 of which are contour. Numerical Chao tones are used to transcribe tones in this paper.

- [33] mid-level
- [35] mid-rising
- [51] high-falling
- [21] low-falling

Sometimes when the high-falling tone /51/ follows a mid-level or low-falling such as [33] or [21], the tone is perceptually [452] or [451] due to transitioning from [33] or [21], and hence there is a contour transition.

The relatively few number of tones in Va is not unusual, as Angkuic languages do not tend to have many tones. For instance, Muak Sa-aak, an Angkuic language of eastern Shan State, Myanmar, has only 3 phonemic tones (Hall 2010).

No stress patterns have been observed in Va, and intonation patterns have not been researched.

2.4 Syllable structure

The permissible syllable structure of Va, which is a monosyllabic tonal language, is as follows.
C(C)V(V)(N/C)^T

- C = Consonant
- V = Vowel
- N = Nasalization
- ^T = Tone

The minimal permissible syllable in Va is CV^T, such as *ma*⁵¹ ‘field’.

Initials usually consist of one consonant, but sometimes they may also consist of two consonants, as with the clusters *kl-*, *k^hl-*, *pl-*, *p^hl-*, and *p^hj-*, as explained in section 2.1.2.

VV occurs only in the case of diphthongs, as there are no long vowels or vowel length contrast in Va.

Note that N refers to the process of nasalization only (which can be alternatively transcribed as \tilde{V}), and not final nasal phonemes such as $-/ŋ/$. Nasalization is contrastive, as shown in section 4. (N/C) is used to signify that when phonemic nasalization occurs, no final consonant is able to occur in the word.

Tones are suprasegmental, and are transcribed using superscript numerals in this paper.

Also, since Va is monosyllabic with isolating morphology, no morphophonemic processes have been observed in the language. Unlike some Angkuic languages such as Muak Sa-aak (Hall 2010), there are no minor syllables (sesquisyllables) in Va.

2.4.1 Ambiguous segments

The affricates $/tʃ/$ and $/dʒ/$ are analyzed as C rather than CC, and diphthongs as V.

The bilabial approximant $/w/$ can only occur at the beginning of a word, as in *woi*⁵¹ ‘fly (insect)’. $/u/$ can occur after the glottal stop $/ʔ/$, as in *kou*²¹*ʔua*⁵¹ ‘earthworm’.

3. Phonetically similar segments

Phonetically similar segments are pairs of phones that show similar phonetic features, and thus can be potential allophones of each other. These are identified below in Figures () and () using bold red lines.

3.1 Consonants

	<i>bilabial</i>	<i>labiodental</i>	<i>alveolar</i>	<i>retroflex</i>	<i>alveolar- palatal</i>	<i>palatal</i>	<i>velar</i>	<i>glottal</i>
<i>voiceless stop</i>	p		t				k	ʔ
<i>aspirated voiceless stop</i>	p ^h		t ^h				k ^h	
<i>voiceless nasal</i>	m		n			ɲ	ŋ	
<i>voiced nasal</i>	m		n			ɲ	ŋ	
<i>voiceless fricative</i>		f	s	ʂ	c		x	h
<i>voiced fricative</i>		v			z		ɣ	
<i>approximant</i>		w						
<i>voiceless affricate</i>					tc			
<i>voiced affricate</i>					dz			
<i>lateral</i>		l						
<i>lateral fricative</i>		ɬ						

Figure 2: Pairs of phonetically similar consonants

3.2 Vowels

	<i>front</i>	<i>central</i>	<i>back</i> <i>unrounded</i>	<i>back</i> <i>rounded</i>
<i>high</i>	i	i	ɯ	u
<i>high-mid</i>	e		ɤ	o
<i>low</i>	a			

Figure 3: Pairs of phonetically similar vowels

4. Contrastive phonemes

Pairs of Va lexical items containing some of the phonetically similar segments listed in section 3 are listed here. They are either *contrastive in identical environments* (henceforth abbreviated as C.I.E.) or *contrastive in analogous environments* (henceforth abbreviated as C.I.E.). Note that these examples are not exhaustive, and that due to the limited data available, these examples are meant to illustrate the most notable phonemic contrasts in Va.

Examples of C.I.E., also known as minimal pairs, can contrast consonants, vowels, or tones, as shown below.

Consonants

ŋei³³ ‘meat’
 ŋei³³ ‘needle’

Vowels

ŋam⁵¹ ‘blood’
 ŋɤm⁵¹ ‘year’

Tones

so³³ ‘dog’
 so⁵¹ ‘dry’

Va also has some homophones, or distinct lexical items with the same phonemic representations but distinct semantic meanings, such as ɲai⁵¹ ‘eye’ and ɲai⁵¹ ‘far’.

4.1 Consonants

Pairs of Va lexical items constrating consonants in identical and analagous environments are given below.

[m] and [p] (C.I.E.)

mua³³ ‘nose’

pua³³ ‘eat, to’

[m] and [ᵿ] (C.I.E.)

ma⁵¹ ‘field’

ᵿa⁵¹ ‘wind’

[l] and [ɭ] (C.A.E.)

lui⁵¹ ‘to run’

ɭut³³ ‘deaf’

[ŋ] and [ŋ̥] (C.A.E.)

ŋa³³ ‘house’

ŋa⁵¹ ‘laugh, to’

[ŋ̥] and [ŋ̥̊] (C.I.E.)

ŋ̥ei³³ ‘meat’

ŋ̥̊ei³³ ‘needle’

[n] and [ŋ] (C.I.E.)

ŋan⁵¹ ‘fire’

ŋaŋ⁵¹ ‘iron’

ʔan⁵¹ ‘big’

ʔaŋ⁵¹ ‘bone’

[m] and [ŋ] (C.A.E.)

ɰam⁵¹ ‘weep, to’

ɰaŋ⁵¹ ‘go, to’

[ŋ] and [ʔ] (C.I.E.)

faŋ⁵¹ ‘to ask’

faʔ⁵¹ ‘monkey’

[k] and [ʔ] (C.I.E.)

lu:k⁵¹ ‘look, to’

luʔ⁵¹ ‘choose, to’

[s] and [ʂ] (C.A.E.)

ʂi³³ ‘rope, string’

si⁵¹ ‘4’

[f] and [v] (C.A.E.)

fai⁵¹ ‘sell, to’

vai²¹ ‘tiger’

4.2 Vowels and diphthongs

Pairs of Va lexical items constrating vowels and diphthongs in identical and analagous environments are given below.

[a] and [ɤ] (C.I.E.)

ɰam⁵¹ ‘blood’

ɰɤm⁵¹ ‘year’

[o] and [u] (C.A.E.)

k^hloŋ⁵¹

k^hluŋ²¹

[ei] and [o] (C.I.E.)

p^hjeiŋ⁵¹ ‘oil’

p^hjoŋ⁵¹ ‘draon’

[i] and [ɣ] (C.I.E.)

plɣ³³ ‘salt’

pli³³ ‘body louse’

[a] and [e] (C.A.E.)

ɬam⁵¹ ‘weep, to’

ɬen⁵¹ ‘die, to’

[o] and [ʉ] (C.I.E.)

ʎo³³ ‘1.sg’

ʎu³³ ‘father’

[o] and [u] (C.A.E.)

k^hloŋ⁵¹ ‘inside’

k^hluŋ²¹ ‘belly’

[u] and [ʉ] (C.I.E.)

tɕua⁵¹ ‘buy, to’

tɕua⁵¹ ‘know, to’

[ã] and [aŋ] (C.I.E.)

ʎã⁵¹ ‘mountain’

ʎaŋ⁵¹ ‘bone’

4.3 Tones

Pairs of Va lexical items constrating tones in identical and analagous environments are given below.

[³³] and [²¹] (C.I.E.)

sau³³ ‘hearth, fireplace’

sau²¹ ‘20’

[³⁵] and [⁵¹] (C.I.E.)

lui³⁵ ‘hit, to’

lui⁵¹ ‘run, to’

[³³] and [⁵¹] (C.I.E.)

so³³ ‘dog’

so⁵¹ ‘dry’

vaŋ³³ ‘door’

vaŋ⁵¹ ‘autonym’

5. Allophones

Only one allophonic rule has been observed, perhaps due to the fact that my transcription of the data had been more phonemic, and all the detailed phonetic nuances of the data were not completely transcribed. The following allophonic rule is a nasal assimilation one.

/m/ > [ŋ] / _ ŋ, ŋ

The lexical items below illustrate this nasal assimilation rule.

ʔum²¹ɕua⁵¹ ‘sweat’ (‘water’ + ‘sweat’)

ʔuŋ²¹ŋai⁵¹ ‘tears’ (‘water’ + ‘eye’)

When this rule applied, /ʔum²¹/ would be the underlying form rather than [ʔuŋ²¹]. This is because /m/ assimilates to the voiceless velar nasal consonant [ŋ] in [ŋai⁵¹], whereas /m/ would not be required to assimilate to the alveolo-palatal fricative [ɕ] in [ɕua⁵¹].

Historical evidence also suggests that /ʔum²¹/ is the underlying form, as Sidwell (2015) reconstructs *ʔom ‘water’ for Proto-Palaungic.

6. Phonotactics

This section discusses some highlights of Va phonotactics, i.e. how phonemes are distributed.

6.1 Consonants

In Va, all consonants can occur word-initially, but only 7 consonants can occur word-finally, as shown in Table 5. As most Tai languages also this identical system of final consonants, this is most likely due to contact with Tai languages. The Tai language which Va would be in contact with is Tai Ya. Southwestern Mandarin (Yunnanese), which Va is in heavy contact with, does not have any final stops.

Table 5: Final consonants

	bilabial	alveolar	velar	glottal
stop	-p	-t	-k	-ʔ
nasal	-m	-n	-ŋ	

6.2 Vowels and diphthongs

Table 6 shows how vowels can co-occur with each other as diphthongs. Rows represent the preceding (first) vowel of a diphthong, while columns represent the following (second) vowel of a diphthong. These correspondences are marked with capital X's in the table below.

Table 6: Phonotactics of diphthongs

	<i>i</i>	<i>ɨ</i>	<i>ʉ</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>ɤ</i>	<i>o</i>	<i>a</i>
<i>i</i>					X			
<i>ɨ</i>								
<i>ʉ</i>								X
<i>u</i>	X							
<i>e</i>	X							
<i>ɤ</i>	X							
<i>o</i>				X				
<i>a</i>								

7. Concluding remarks

This paper has presented a preliminary phonological sketch of a virtually unknown and highly underdocumented language. However, the analysis here is still very preliminary, and much more work remains to be done. Furthermore, the audio recordings were also not very clear and had some distortions, since the microphone was held too close to the informant.

Below are some problems that have not been completely resolved in this paper.

- Transcription of nasalized vowel (\tilde{V}) vs. vowel with final velar nasal ($V\eta$)
- Transcriptions of tone values: Should $[^{33}]$ be $[^{44}]$ or $[^{55}]$? Should $[^{21}]$ be $[^{11}]$? Studies on tone sandhi will need to be done in order to sort out these issues.

Suggestions for further fieldwork projects include the following.

- Collection of vocabulary lists beyond 300 words
- Grammar and texts, none of which exist for Va to my knowledge
- Survey of language varieties, geographic locations, and sociolinguistic situation
- Documentation of Southern Va of Zhenlong, which is much more endangered than Northern Va and, to my knowledge, has never been documented before prior to my 2014 visit
- Ethnographic studies of the Va people

References

- Hall, Elizabeth. 2010. *A Phonology of Muak Sa-aak*. M.A. thesis. Chiang Mai, Thailand: Payap University.
- Hsiu, Andrew. 2015. *The Angkuic languages: a preliminary survey*. Presentation given at ICAAL 6 (6th International Conference on Austroasiatic Linguistics), Siem Reap, Cambodia.
- Simao Prefecture Ethnic Minority Affairs Bureau [思茅行署民族事务委员会] (ed). 1990. *A study of the Bulang people* [布朗族研究]. m.s.
- Sidwell, Paul. 2015. *The Palaungic Languages: Classification, Reconstruction and Comparative Lexicon*. München: Lincom Europa.
- Svantesson, Jan-Olof. 1988. "U." In *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area*, 11 , no. 1: 64-133.
- Zhou Yaowen [周耀文]. 2001. *A Study of Dai Dialects* [傣语方言研究]. Beijing: Ethnic Publishing House [民族出版社].

Appendix 1: Preliminary transcription of Northern Va

Below is a preliminary transcription of Northern Va, with 246 lexical items included. Brief etymological comments are given in the right-most column.

<i>English gloss</i>	<i>Va, Northern</i>	<i>Syllable structure</i>	<i>Comments</i>
1	tiʔ ³³	CVCT	
2	ka ⁵¹	CVT	
3	kui ⁵¹	CVVCT	
4	si ⁵¹	CVT	Tai loanword
5	ha ³⁵	CVT	Tai loanword
6	hok ³³	CVCT	Tai loanword
7	tɕɤt ³³	CVCT	Tai loanword
8	pet ³³	CVCT	Tai loanword
9	kau ³⁵	CVVT	Tai loanword
10	sip ³³	CVCT	Tai loanword
20	sau ²¹	CVVT	Tai loanword
100	tiʔ ³³ pak ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
200	ka ⁵¹ pak ⁵¹	CVC	
1000	tiʔ ³³ ɕin ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
2000	ka ⁵¹ ɕin ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
10000	tiʔ ³³ van ³³	CVCT.CVCT	
ant	mut ³³	CVCT	
arrow	ʔaɾ ⁵¹	CVCT	
ash	p ^h luŋ ³⁵ ŋaŋ ⁵¹	CCVCT.CVCT	
ask	faŋ ⁵¹	CVT	
autonym	vaɾ ⁵¹	CVCT	autonym similar to "Wa" but language not Waic
ax	mɤi ⁵¹	CVVT	
back	ma ²¹ ɲua ⁵¹	CVT.CVVT	
bad	tɕuɾ ³³	CVT	

bamboo	ŋum ³³ xɿŋ ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
banana	p ^h li ²¹ to ³³	CCVT.CVT	
bear	k ^h ua ⁵¹	CVVT	
bed	ku ⁵¹	CVT	
bee	sie ⁵¹	CVVT	
behind	lu ²¹ kaŋ ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
belly	k ^h luŋ ²¹	CCVCT	
big	ʔan ⁵¹	CVCT	
bird	sim ³³	CVCT	
bite	kak ³³	CVCT	
bitter	saŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
black	laŋ ⁵¹ plon ⁵¹	CVCT.CCVCT	Palaungic innovation
blind	liau ⁵¹	CVVVT	
blood	ŋam ⁵¹	CVCT	
boat	lon ⁵¹	CVVNT	
bone	ʔaŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
brain	t ^h ok ⁵¹	CVCT	
branch	taŋ ²¹ si ^{ʔ33}	CVCT.CVT	
breasts	pu ³³	CVT	
bridge	t ^h uk ³³	CVCT	
buffalo	k ^h ua ^{ʔ51}	CVVCT	
Va language	tou ⁵¹ wo ²¹ va ^{ʔ51}	CVVT.CVT.CVCT	
burn, to	pu ^{ʔ33}	CVVT	
butterfly	p ^h ai ²¹ ʔa ^{ʔ33}	CVCT.CVCT	
buy, to	tɕua ⁵¹	CVVT	
chew, to	pem ⁵¹	CVCT	
chicken	ʔie ⁵¹	CVVT	
child	k ^h o ²¹ nom ⁵¹	CVC.CVCT	
choose, to	lu ^{ʔ51}	CVCT	
chopsticks	t ^h ua ³³	CVVT	
clothes	num ³³	CVCT	

cloud	m̥ouʔ ⁵¹	CVVCT	
come	laʔ ³³	CVCT	
cook, to	tʰsa ²¹	CVT	
cattle	vu ²¹	CVT	
crab	t ^h am ⁵¹	CVCT	
cry, weep	z̥am ⁵¹	CVCT	
cut, hack	kɣt ³³	CVCT	
day	ŋi ³³	CVT	
daytime	taŋ ²¹ ŋi ³³	CVCT.CVT	
deaf	tut ³³	CVCT	
die, to	z̥en ⁵¹	CVCT	Palaungic innovation
dig, to	mak ³³	CVCT	
dog	so ³³	CVT	
door	vaʔ ³³	CVCT	
dragon	p ^h joŋ ⁵¹	CVVCT	
dream, to	mi ³³	CVT	
drink, to	t ^h eiŋ ²¹	CVVCT	
dry	so ⁵¹	CVT	
duck	pet ³³	CVCT	Tai loanword
dust	k ^h liʔ ³³	CCVCT	
ear	ɕu ²¹ ɕu ⁵¹	CVT.CVT	
earth	teiʔ ³³	CVVCT	
earthworm	kou ²¹ ʔua ⁵¹	CVNT.CVVT	
eat, to	pua ³³	CVVT	
eat rice	k ^h o ²¹ k ^h ai ⁵¹	CVT.CVVT	
egg	t ^h am ³³	CVCT	Palaungic innovation
eye	ŋai ⁵¹	CVVT	Palaungic innovation
face	t ^h aŋ ³⁵ ŋai ⁵¹	CVCT.CVVT	
fall, to	k ^h liʔ ³³	CCVCT	
far	ŋai ⁵¹	CVVT	homonym with 'eye'
fat	k ^h lɣn ⁵¹	CCVCT	

father	ʔu ³³	CVT	
fear, to	ɣɣt ³³	CVCT	
female, woman	k ^h on ²¹ p ^h ɣŋ ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
field	ma ⁵¹	CVT	
fire	ŋan ⁵¹	CVCT	Palaungic innovation
fish	k ^h aŋ ³³	CVCT	
flower	ɣaŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
fly, to	p ^h ua ⁵¹	CVVT	
fly (insect)	woi ⁵¹	CVVT	
forest	p ^h aŋ ²¹ si ³³	CVCT.CVT	
frog	ɕek ³³	CVCT	
front side	loŋ ³⁵ ŋai ⁵¹	CVCT.CVVT	
fruit	p ^h li ²¹ vei ³³	CCVT.CVVT	
ghost	kuŋ ³³	CVCT	
go, to	zəŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
good	zoŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
goose	haŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
green; blue	vei ²¹ ŋia ³³	CVVT.CVVT	
grow, to	ʔa ²¹ la ³³	CVNT.CCV	
hair (of head)	suk ²¹ tɕ ^h iŋ ⁵¹	CVC.CVCT	
Han Chinese	k ^h a ⁵¹	CVT	
hand	t ^h iŋ ³³	CVT	Germanic-type shift (= Angkuic?)
head	tɕ ^h iŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	palatalized from P-Palaungic
hear, to	ŋaŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	homonym with 'fire'
heart	mu ²¹ ɕak ³³	CVT.CVCT	
hearth, fireplace	sau ³³	CVVT	
heavy	tseŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
here	ni ²¹ to ³³	CVT.CVVT	
hit, to	lui ³⁵	CVVT	
horse	puaŋ ⁵¹	CVVCT	

house	na ³³	CVT	
hunt, to	p ^h ɲ ³⁵ tia ⁵¹	CVCT.CVVT	
husband	mei ³³ mi ³³	CVVT.CVT	
insect	koŋ ⁵¹	CVVT	
inside	k ^h loŋ ⁵¹	CCVVT	
intestines	vek ³³	CVCT	
iron	ŋaŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	homonym with 'fire'
kill, to	ŋeɿ ³³	CVT	
knee	ŋum ³³ saŋ ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
knife	zot ⁵¹	CVCT	
knit, to	kua ⁵¹	CVVT	
know, to	dzuwa ⁵¹	CVVT	
laugh, to	na ⁵¹	CVT	
leaf	ɬa ²¹ siɿ ³³	CVT.CVT	
left side	fai ⁵¹ veiɿ ³⁵	CVVT.CVVCT	
leg	tsɿ ⁵¹	CVNT	
live, to	ɿim ⁵¹	CVCT	
liver	t ^h om ⁵¹	CVCT	
long	lã ⁵¹	CVNT	
look, to	luuk ⁵¹	CVCT	
louse, body	pli ³³	CCVT	
louse, head	tɕ ^h iŋ ²¹ ɕi ³³	CVCT.CVT	ɕi ³³ < Chinese 'louse'
lung	puɿ ²¹	CVT	
male, man	ɿiɿ ²¹ k ^h uŋ ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
meat	ŋei ³³	CVVT	
medicine	si ²¹ si ³³	CVT.CVT	
money	seŋ ³⁵	CVCT	Chinese dialect loan?
monkey	faɿ ⁵¹	CVT	
moon	tɕ ^h ie ⁵¹	CVVT	palatalized from P-Palaungic
mosquito	juŋ ²¹ jaŋ ³³	CVCT.CVCT	
mother	mei ³³	CVVT	

mountain	ʔã ⁵¹	CVNT	
mouth	mõ ⁵¹	CVNT	
mushroom	t ^h ie ³³	CVVT	
name	mie ³³ mi ³³	CVVT.CVT	
navel	tuʔ ³³	CVCT	
near	teiʔ ³³	CVVCT	
neck	ŋaɾ ⁵¹	CVT	
needle	ŋei ³³	CVVT	
new	xu ³³	CVT	
night	ta ³³ sim ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
nose	mua ³³	CVCT	
oil	p ^h jeinj ⁵¹	CV	
old (of people)	teŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
old (of objects)	p ^h ɣt ³³	CVCT	
outside	laŋ ³⁵ nok ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
person, human	ʔiʔ ³³	CVCT	
pig	lik ⁵¹	CVCT	
pillars	kuaŋ ⁵¹	CVVCT	
plant, to	t ^h ui ⁵¹	CVVT	
plough, to	t ^h ai ⁵¹	CVVT	
I	ʔo ³³	CVT	
you (sg.)	mi ³³	CVT	
he, she	t ^h a ³³	CVT	
we	ʔei ³³	CVVT	
you (pl.)	p ^h ei ³³	CVVT	
they	kei ⁵¹	CVVT	
rabbit	t ^h u ³³ la ⁵¹	CVT.CVT	
rain	tɕũi ⁵¹	CVVNT	
rat	sik ⁵¹	CVCT	
red	ve ²¹ ŋam ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
rice, cooked	k ^h ai ⁵¹	CVVT	

rice, grain	k ^h u ³³	CVT	
rice, plant	ŋou ³³	CVVT	
right side	fai ⁵¹ sam ⁵¹	CVVT.CVCT	
river	ʔuŋ ²¹ ʔua ³³	CVCT.CVCT	
road	kuoŋ ⁵¹	CVVCT	
root	ɣua ²¹ vei ³³	CVVT.CVVT	
rope; string	ʂi ³³	CVT	
run, to	lui ⁵¹	CVVT	
salt	plɤ ³³	CCVT	
say, to	to ⁵¹	CVT	
sell, to	fai ⁵¹	CVVT	
sew, to	p ^h aŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
sheep	pei ^{ʔ33}	CVVCT	
shoes	tɕiep ³³	CVVCT	
shoot, to	p ^h ɤŋ ³³	CVCT	
short	tot ³³ , pɤ ²¹ tot ³³	CVCT, CVT.CVCT	
shoulder	kloŋ ³³	CCVCT	
sick	ɕu ³³	CVT	
sit, to	ŋom ⁵¹	CVCT	
skin	kɤ ³³	CVT	
skirt	num ³³ ja ⁵¹	CVCT.CVT	
sky	puŋ ⁵¹	CVCT	
sleep	ʔei ⁵¹ tɤ ²¹	CVVT.CVT	
small	pek ³³	CVCT	
smoke (of fire)	m̥un ³⁵ ŋan ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	
snake	sɤn ⁵¹	CVCT	
sniff/smell, to	vui ²¹	CVVT	
snow	t ^h aʔ ⁵¹	CVCT	
sorghum	soŋ ³⁵ p ^h li ³³	CVCT.CCVT	
sour	sa ⁵¹	CVT	
spider	m̥un ²¹ pua ⁵¹	CVCT.CVVT	

stairs	tua ⁵¹	CVVT	
stand	jɣk ³³	CVCT	
star	m̥un ⁵¹	CVCT	
steal, to	ɣaɿ ³³	CVT	
stone	lu ²¹ m̥o ³³	CVT.CVT	
suck, to	nɣt ⁵¹	CVCT	
sugarcane	kuoŋ ³⁵ mei ³³	CVCT.CVVT	
sun	ŋai ²¹ ŋi ³³	CVVT.CVT	‘eye-day’
sweat	ʔum ²¹ ɕua ⁵¹	CVC.CVVT	
sweet	ŋeiŋ ⁵¹	CVVCT	
swell	ɕaɿ ³³	CVCT	
swim, to	loi ⁵¹	CVVT	
tail	ta ³³	CVCT	
tears	ʔuŋ ²¹ ŋai ⁵¹	CVCT.CVVT	‘water-eye’
there	ne ²¹ to ³³	CVT.CVVT	
thick	sɣt ³³	CVCT	
thin	ɕie ⁵¹	CVVT	
tiger	vai ²¹	CVVT	
tobacco	ja ⁵¹	CVT	
tongue	ʔa ²¹ t ^h ak ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
tooth	xuã ⁵¹	CVVNT	
tree; wood	ŋum ³⁵ si ³³	CVC.CVT	
trousers, pants	tiu ⁵¹	CVVT	
turtle	teik ⁵¹	CVVCT	
vomit, to	ku ³³	CVCT	
wall	sun ³⁵	CVCT	
water	ʔuŋ ³⁵ ŋan ⁵¹	CVCT.CVCT	ŋaŋ ⁵¹ = ‘fire’
wet	xu ³³	CVT	
what (interrogative)	ʔa ²¹ mou ³³	CVT.CVVT	
white	ve ²¹ paŋ ⁵¹	CVT.CVCT	
who	mai ³⁵	CVVT	

(interrogative)			
wife	p ^h ɣŋ ³³ mi ³³	CVCT.CVT	
wind	ma ⁵¹	CVT	
wine, liquor	ʔũ ⁵¹	CVVT	
wing	p ^h ie ⁵¹	CVVT	
year	ŋɣm ⁵¹	CVCT	
yellow	ve ²¹ ɬũ ⁵¹	CVT.CVNT	